

**MENTAL HEALTH LITERACY, PSYCHOLOGICAL WELL-BEING, AND
ATTACHMENT STYLES AS PREDICTORS OF HELP-SEEKING
BEHAVIORS: IMPLICATIONS FOR A RECALIBRATED
SCHOOL-BASED MENTAL HEALTH PROGRAM**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 31

Issue 1

Pages: 1-12

Document ID: 2025PEMJ2937

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14717577

Manuscript Accepted: 01-14-2025

Mental Health Literacy, Psychological Well-being, and Attachment Styles as Predictors of Help-Seeking Behaviors: Implications for a Recalibrated School-based Mental Health Program

Mark Vincent F. Reyes,* Sheila Marie G. Hocson
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Global research on effective, evidence-based school-based mental health programs remains limited, with mental health services in many regions, including the Philippines, often underutilized. In the Philippines, the growing mental health concerns among students are exacerbated by a significant shortage of qualified mental health professionals. This study aimed to examine predictors of help-seeking behaviors among students at a private university in the Philippines and to provide insights for the recalibration of school-based mental health programs. Using a descriptive correlational research design, the researcher employed four standardized instruments to gather data, which were subsequently analyzed through multiple regression analysis. The findings revealed that students exhibited high levels of mental health literacy ($X = 123.98$, $SD = 11.05$) and help-seeking behaviors ($X = 6.12$, $SD = 1.06$), although their psychological well-being was only at an average level ($X = 51.11$, $SD = 11.24$). Additionally, fearful attachment styles were prevalent among the students ($f = 406$). The analysis further showed that mental health literacy, the mental health inventory, and the "close" dimension of attachment styles were the strongest predictors of help-seeking behaviors, as indicated by an F-statistic of 55.15 and a p-value of $< .05$. This suggests that the model explained a significant portion of the variance in help-seeking behaviors. The adjusted R-squared value of .22 indicates that these predictors accounted for approximately 22% of the variability in help-seeking behaviors. These findings have informed the development of a recalibrated school-based mental health program with a focus on improving mental health literacy, enhancing help-seeking behaviors, and addressing fearful attachment styles among students.

Keywords: *master of arts in psychology, mental health literacy, psychological well-being, attachment styles*

Introduction

From birth through adulthood, mental health is essential (SAMHSA, 2022). To effectively advocate for, safeguard, and improve mental health, it is critical to support initiatives that promote mental health awareness such as organizing events to promote mental health awareness and disseminate relevant mental resources. This includes creating mental health services that are located in institutions.

25% of World Health Organization (WHO) member states or 31% of responding nations worldwide, have reported integrating mental health into basic healthcare. Additionally, mental hospitals have a restricted number of beds. In terms of outpatient visits, high-income countries have about 5000 visits per 100,000 individuals, compared to 100 visits per 100,000 in low-income ones (WHO, 2020). According to the Mental Health Atlas (2020), there are less than two outpatient clinics and less than 0.5 inpatient facilities for every 100,000 children and adolescents. This merely demonstrated the dearth of mental health facilities and the poor use of mental health treatments. The WHO's Mental Health Action Plan stressed the value of promoting mental health, especially throughout a person's early years. In low- and middle-income countries, many people with severe mental illnesses, ranging from 76% to 85%, do not receive the necessary treatment for their condition (Mental Health Action Plan, 2019).

According to Mental Health Atlas (2020), 17% of the 420 operational mental health initiatives were listed on mental health promotion and prevention in schools. Research on successful evidence-based school-based mental health initiatives in the educational context is scarce worldwide, and the majority of studies regarded mental health literacy as an outcome measure (Xu et al., 2020). Despite the abundance of publications presenting effective school-based mental health efforts, current results showed a notable lack of consensus around what constitutes mental health in schools and related concepts (Cavioni et al., 2020). This was corroborated from the research of Nishio et al. (2020), which claimed that there was a dearth of mental health services in schools, raising interest in creating a school-based mental health program to help kids with their mental health.

Golberstein et al. (2020) state that one service that educational institutions may miss is the provision of mental health services. According to a systematic review of children and adolescents' use of mental health services in the US by Duong et al. (2021), 22.10% of youth with elevated diagnoses or symptoms of mental illness received care in school-based health services, compared to 7.28% of the general youth population. This was validated by a study of Ali et al. (2018), which found that students were more likely to seek mental health services outside of schools for serious mental health issues and that adolescents were more likely to seek mental health services in schools for issues relating to friends, family, and school. Additionally, there was a higher likelihood of mental health services being used in a school context by students from lower socioeconomic backgrounds.

In addition to the rise in mental health issues among Filipino students, there was a dearth of mental health specialists who could offer students mental health support. In the Philippines, there are two to three mental health professionals for every 100,000 people (Lally, Tully, & Samaniego, 2019; Villa, 2022). As of June 2022, there are just 4,069 guidance counselors, with a ratio of one counselor for every 500 students (Bacelonia, 2022). The effective provision of mental health services was impacted by the shortage of mental health

specialists.

The Philippine Mental Health Law was passed in order to safeguard, advance, and improve mental health in the country. It also known as Republic Act 11036, passed on June 21, 2018, marking the beginning of the recognition of every Filipino's fundamental right to mental health (Senate of the Philippines, 2018). Its mission is to enhance the well-being of Filipinos by offering everyone access to high-quality mental health care. Additionally, the law guarantees the protection, promotion, and acknowledgement of mental health. The law also requires the development, implementation, and evaluation of national policies on mental health, campaigns, and laws, as well as the integration of these approaches into communities, organizations, and educational institutions (Senate of the Philippines, 2018).

There are other mental health-related policies in place in addition to the Philippine Mental Health Law. The Anti-Bullying Act, which prohibits and addresses bullying in schools; the Safe Spaces Act; which addresses all instances of sexual harassment based on gender; the Anti-Hazing Law, which monitors initiatory rituals, including as hazing, in sorority and fraternity groups. and various other groups to prevent shameful events that can result in either psychological or physical damage (The LAWPHil Project, n.d.). These laws support people's mental health. These could be included in comprehensive, standardized mental health initiatives at schools that offer targeted or specific populations programs from the general public.

The epidemic and the government's lack of effective mental health measures have both deteriorated the mental health and wellbeing of young Filipinos (Malolos et al., 2021). The Philippines' economic situation and the lack of mental health interventions make it difficult for citizens to receive mental health care (Lally et al., 2019). It was also observed that when mental health services are offered in an educational setting, there is a greater chance that the diagnosis and progress assessment will be more accurate due to the easy access to data regarding students' functioning in social, academic, and physical environments.

In response to these growing concerns, the Philippine Council on Mental Health has made it one of its goals to incorporate measures promoting mental health in workplaces, educational institutions, and communities. The council aims to develop evidence-based interventions for young people's socio-emotional abilities.

According to the aforementioned studies, mental health issues are becoming more prevalent in the Philippines, and there are insufficient resources available to meet the demands of the country's citizens in this regard. Creating a school-based mental health program that will address the mental health needs of youths and identify young children who require further in-depth assistance for specific mental health issues is essential.

In the context of this study, an institutionalized mental health program is currently in place. Though the program is still in its beginnings, it ought to be strengthened, particularly with regard to encouraging students to take advantage of the university's mental health services. There are numerous reasons why students look for mental health aid. In order to create a school-based mental health program and precisely identify kids who require specialist clinical treatment for their mental health problem, this study investigated the predictors of help-seeking behaviors among students.

According to Section 24 of the Mental Health Act, educational institutions must develop policies and initiatives to promote mental health among students, teachers, and staff. These measures should include increasing awareness of psychological issues, identifying and providing support for those at risk, and ensuring access to resources and services. Additionally, they should facilitate the referral of individuals with mental health disorders to appropriate treatment and psychosocial support within the institution.

The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between students' help-seeking behaviors at a private university in the Philippines and mental health literacy, psychological well-being, and attachment styles. The findings of this study would be used to reevaluate school-based mental health programs, with a particular focus on creating an internal referral unit for high-risk and specialized mental health issues. This study also served as a reference for assessing school-based mental health programs in accordance with RA 11036, popularly known as the Philippine Mental Health Law, since there is currently no set structure for creating such programs.

This study is anchored on Multi-Tiered System of Support Theory by Lightner Witner (1896). The Multi-Tiered System of Support will be the backbone of this study as the researcher explores how mental health literacy, psychological well-being, and attachment styles predict help-seeking behaviors of students to develop a school-based mental health program. The results of the study will aid in developing programs and activities per tier to support the mental health of students in school.

The accumulated related literature and studies were arranged to discuss the concepts, practices, and related studies pertaining to mental health literacy, psychological well-being, attachment styles, help-seeking behaviors, and school-based mental health programs.

In order to examine the theories, methods, and relevant research on mental health literacy, psychological well-being, attachment types, help-seeking behaviors, and school-based mental health initiatives, a collection of relevant literature and studies was assembled.

Mental Health literacy encompasses understanding mental disorders, recognizing risk factors and causes, knowledge of interventions, awareness of available help, supportive attitudes towards seeking help, and knowing where to find mental health information (Sampaio et al., 2022; Canberra, 2020). Socioeconomic status (Rey et al., 2022) and educational institution type (Argao et al., 2021) significantly impact MHL levels. Factors such as gender and educational level also play roles; for instance, male students and undergraduates tend

to exhibit lower MHL (Cormie et al., 2022). Studies indicate that despite recognizing mental health issues, stigma and normalization of symptoms often prevent timely help-seeking (Ines, 2019). Filipino college students, for example, are aware of professional help but prefer seeking support from friends and family (Ines, 2019). Studies generally indicate a positive correlation between higher MHL and increased likelihood of seeking professional help (Goodfellow et al., 2022; Iswanto & Ayubi, 2023). However, internalized stigma and preferences for self-reliance can delay or deter help-seeking behaviors, despite adequate mental health literacy (Lumaksono et al., 2020). Effective interventions should also reduce barriers and enhance support systems to encourage help-seeking behaviors.

While mental health literacy is crucial in promoting understanding of mental health issues, its direct correlation with help-seeking behaviors is mixed. Some studies suggest that higher mental health literacy is associated with increased likelihood of seeking help (Saito & Creedy, 2021), whereas others indicate that it may not significantly influence actual help-seeking behaviors (Amado-Rodriguez et al., 2022).

Studies also consistently highlight high levels of psychological distress among college students, with symptoms of anxiety, stress, and depression being prevalent (Liu et al., 2019). Freshmen often experience heightened anxiety, while sophomore students tend to report increased stress and depression. These findings underscore the need for targeted psychological support tailored to students' varying needs based on their academic progression. The COVID-19 pandemic exacerbated existing mental health challenges among college students, leading to increased feelings of loneliness, fear, anxiety, and potential depression (Egcas et al., 2021). This global crisis underscored the importance of proactive mental health interventions and support systems within educational settings. Establishing help desks and providing targeted psychological assistance emerged as critical strategies to address immediate and long-term mental health impacts.

In terms of attachment styles, Secure attachment styles, characterized by trust and comfort in relationships, are associated with better emotional regulation and overall mental health outcomes (Salinas-Quiroz & Dominguez-Espinosa, 2023). Conversely, insecure attachment styles, such as anxious or avoidant, can lead to difficulties in managing emotions and coping with stressors, thereby increasing vulnerability to mental health issues (Vowels et al., 2023; Vismara, Lucarelli, & Sechi, 2022). Research indicates that individuals with anxious attachment styles may struggle more with emotional regulation compared to those with secure or avoidant styles (Henschel et al., 2020). This difficulty can impact interpersonal relationships and overall psychological well-being. Recognizing the impact of early attachment experiences can guide in preventive approach that fosters secure attachments and promotes psychological well-being. Understanding attachment styles can inform the development of effective interventions, such as school-based mental health programs. These programs could be tailored to address the specific needs of individuals with different attachment styles, promoting secure attachments and facilitating help-seeking behaviors (Lu et al., 2022).

Research have also shown that education and awareness, peer and family support, and technological resources should be the focus of programs to be developed (Velasco et al., 2019; Ishikawa et al., 2022; Pretorius et al., 2019). Moreover, tailored interventions and policy initiatives that promote mental health awareness, reduce stigma, and improve access to culturally sensitive mental health services are crucial in enhancing mental health outcomes (Xiong & Yang, 2020; Jacobs & Pentaris, 2021). Programs can effectively support mental health needs of students by integrating evidence-based practices and adapting to evolving challenges on mental health.

Integrating knowledge from studies on MHL, psychological well-being, attachment styles, help-seeking behaviors, and school-based mental health programs provides a comprehensive framework for developing effective interventions. These interventions should be responsive to diverse needs, incorporate evidence-based practices, and foster supportive educational environments that promote mental health awareness and resilience among students. Continued research and policy initiatives are essential for advancing these efforts and ensuring equitable access to mental health support within educational settings.

There is a need to address these growing mental health concerns among college students in the Philippines. By examining factors such as mental health literacy, psychological well-being, attachment styles, and help-seeking behaviors, the study sheds light on critical areas where interventions can be targeted to improve student mental health outcomes. Empirical evidence can be utilized in the development of the recalibrated school-based mental health program. While the study significantly advances our understanding of mental health issues among college students in the Philippines and proposes practical interventions, ongoing research and collaborative efforts are essential to address the identified gaps and ensure that effective mental health support systems are established and maintained within educational settings globally.

This study investigated how mental health literacy, psychological well-being, and attachment styles predict help-seeking behaviors among the school community as a basis for the development of a recalibrated school-based mental health program. Specifically, it sought to answer the level of mental health literacy as perceived by the Mental Health Literacy Scale, the level of psychological well-being as perceived by the Mental Health Inventory in terms of psychological well-being, psychological distress, global mental health index, and mental health index sub scales, the level of attachment styles as perceived by the Adult Attachment Scale in terms of secure, fearful, and dismissive attachment, and the level of help-seeking behaviors as perceived by the Mental Help-seeking Attitude Scale. It also sought to explore how mental health literacy, psychological well-being, and attachment styles predict help-seeking behaviors among students. Lastly, the study sought to explore what school-based mental health program can be developed based on the results of the study.

Methodology

Descriptive correlational method of research was utilized in the study because it seeks to find out how mental health literacy, psychological well-being, and attachment styles predict help-seeking behaviors among students. Additionally, quantitative methods were utilized as the researchers used numerical data from the respondents through the survey questionnaire.

In this research, the participants were 578 students from all year levels represented by all schools, colleges, and departments who were currently enrolled in the second semester of school year 2023-2024 at Centro Escolar University-Manila and were willing to participate in the study. Stratified Purposive Sampling was utilized in the study. To qualify as a respondent, one must be currently enrolled in the second semester of school year 2023-2024 at Centro Escolar University Manila campus.

The researcher used four standardized instruments to gather data: the Mental Health Literacy Scale by O'Connor and Casey (2015), which has a test-retest reliability of .797 and a Cronbach's alpha of .873, to assess participants' mental health literacy. This scale evaluates individuals' ability to recognize mental health disorders, seek information, understand risk factors and causes, be familiar with self-help techniques, and acknowledge the accessibility of professional assistance, while also gauging their attitudes toward appropriate help-seeking behaviors. The Mental Health Inventory by Veit and Ware (1983), with a Cronbach's alpha of .94, was used to measure psychological well-being. This tool assesses general emotional functioning through subscales for anxiety, depression, behavioral control, positive affect, and general distress. The Adult Attachment Scale by Collins and Read (1990) was employed to determine attachment styles, with a Cronbach's alpha of .69 for avoidant attachment, .75 for anxious/ambivalent attachment, and .72 for secure attachment. This scale uses a five-point Likert-type scale to classify individuals' attachment styles. Finally, the Mental Help-Seeking Attitudes Scale by Hammer, Parent, and Spiker, which has an internal consistency of .92 and a test-retest reliability of .76, was used to measure attitudes toward seeking mental health support. This nine-item scale assesses respondents' general opinions—positive or negative—regarding their likelihood of seeking professional help if they were to experience a mental health issue.

The data gathered were tabulated, analyzed and interpreted accordingly using percentage distribution, arithmetic mean, Pearson-r Correlation, Multiple Regression analysis, and stepwise regression analysis.

Results and Discussion

The study's results are presented in this chapter, with tabular and textual interpretations of the level of mental health literacy, psychological well-being, attachment styles, and help-seeking behaviors as a basis for the development of a recalibrated school-based mental health program.

Level of Mental Health Literacy

Table 1. *Mental Health Literacy*

<i>Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>S.D.</i>	<i>V.I.</i>
Average	5	0.9			
High	396	68.5	123.98	11.05	High
Very High	177	30.6			
Total	578	100			

Legend: Very Low: 0-32; Low: 33-65; Average: 66-97; High: 98-129; Very High: 130-160

Table 1 showed that the majority of the respondents have a high level of mental health literacy with the frequency of 396 and a percentage of 68.5. The mean score of the respondents are 123.98 and an SD of 11.05 with a High verbal interpretation. 177 or 30.6 percent of the respondents have a Very High level of mental health literacy while 5 or 0.9 percent of the respondents have an Average level of mental health literacy.

Majority of the respondents can recognize specific disorders, demonstrate knowledge and beliefs about the etiology of the disorders and how to seek information and help about mental health. However, there are still some respondents who are unsure where to seek for mental health support. Additionally, there are still some respondents who believe that people with mental illness could snap out of it if they wanted. There are also respondents who see that mental illness is a sign of personal weakness and perceive that people with mental illness are dangerous. Mental health stigma is still present despite the high level of mental health literacy. There are still respondents who are neither unwilling nor willing to socialize or be involved with someone with mental illness.

In contrast to the study of Gorczyński et al. (2020), Cormier et al. (2022) and Argao et al (2021), the respondents of this study showed higher mental health literacy. Consistent with the study of Ines (2019), some respondents may still hold personal and perceived stigma towards individuals with mental health illnesses. The majority of the respondents were able to recognize mental health disorders and were aware that they could seek help from mental health professionals if they need to. Many students were able to identify mental health disorders based on their presenting symptoms and were familiar with behaviors or actions that will help in preventing mental health concerns. Additionally, most of the respondents demonstrated familiarity with the ethical considerations about mental health. Finally, the respondents were confident where to seek information or resources about mental illness. They also tend to reduce stigmatizing views about mental health and seek help.

This result is supported by the study of Iswanto and Ayubi (2023) who mentioned that there was a relationship with mental health literacy and help-seeking behaviors. In contrast, Adivisio (2022), found out that despite the high level of mental health literacy, there were still barriers to accessing mental health services. These included the cost of the services and lack of knowledge about the resources. Additionally, Lumaksono et al. (2020) claimed that despite a high level of help-seeking and mental health literacy, internalized stigma might be a culprit in seeking professional help thus delaying the mental health services that they receive.

Level of Psychological Well-being

Psychological Well-being

Table 2. Psychological Well Being

Level	Frequency	Percent	Mean	S.D.	V.I.
Low	8	1.4			
Average	391	67.6	51.11	11.24	Average
High	179	31			
Total	578	100			

Legend: Low: 0-28; Average: 29-56; High: 57-84

Table 2 shows that respondents have an average level of psychological well-being with a mean of 51.15 and an SD of 11.24. The frequency distribution claims that there are 391 students who have Average psychological well-being which comprises 67.6 percent of the population. In addition, 179 or 31 percent of the population have a High level of psychological well-being while 8 or 1.4 percent of the population have a Low level of psychological well-being. Then, majority of the students express no significant problems or unfavorable symptoms with regards to their mental health. Respondents are sometimes fairly satisfied and sometimes fairly unhappy with their personal life during the past month. Although they feel generally satisfied with life, they sometimes feel lonely and anxious. The respondents are also hopeful and promising about the future. However, there respondents who feel depressed, nervous, and restless during the past month. Although they are generally happy and hopeful with their life, there are still moments where they feel so down and felt like crying.

The results are similar to the study of Argao et al. (2021) where they found out that the mental health of Filipino students was on average. Majority of the respondents felt capable and satisfied with life. They can function normally in terms of cognition, health, and relationships. The respondents' expressed that they were satisfied with life, positive affect generally, and have good emotional ties. A small number of respondents have a low level of psychological well-being who may feel negative feelings such as loneliness, fear, anxiety, and possibly leading to depression. This is quite similar to the study of Liu et al. (2019) who found out that majority of the freshmen and sophomore students had higher scores on depression, anxiety, and stress. In this study, there were still some students who felt anxious and in the low mood.

Psychological Distress

Table 3. Psychological Distress

Level	Frequency	Percent	Mean	S.D.	V.I.
Low	13	2.2			
Average	435	75.3	80.87	17.55	Average
High	130	22.5			
Total	578	100			

Legend: Low: 0-28; Average: 29-56; High: 57-84

In terms of the level of psychological distress, Table 3 reveals that 435 or 75.3 percent of the population have an average level of psychological distress with a mean of 80.87 and an SD of 17.55. 130 or 22.5 percent of the population have a high level of psychological distress and 13 or 2.2 percent of the population have a Low level of psychological distress. Although majority of the respondents feel good, capable, and satisfied with life, there are still some respondents who feel downhearted, anxious, and worried. In addition, some of them feel difficulty in relaxing during the past months.

In contrast to the many studies conducted on youth (Argao et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Atherton & Cornwall, 2022; Egcas et al., 2021), respondents of this study score average on Psychological distress. Although there are a number of students who scored high on psychological distress ($f=130$), the majority of the respondents feel functional and capable and feel satisfied with many aspects of life. They show less unfavorable concerns or problems related to mental health. Majority of the respondents presented that they have an average level of anxiety, depression, and loss of behavioral or emotional control.

Global Mental Health Index

Table 4 reveals that 274 or 47.4 percent of the population score Average on the Global Mental Health Index and 268 or 46.4 percent of the population score High on the Global Mental Health Index with a mean of 136.34 and an SD of 25.10. 19 or 3.3 percent score low, and 17 or 2.9 percent scored Very High on the Global Mental Health Index. The mental health status of the majority of the respondents is high. This showed that they experience greater psychological wellbeing and relatively less psychological distress. They

showed more favorable mental health symptoms and less frequent occurrence of negative mental health symptoms.

Table 4. *Global Mental Health Index*

<i>Level</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>S.D.</i>	<i>V.I.</i>
Low	19	3.3			
Average	274	47.4			
High	268	46.4	136.34	25.10	High
Very High	17	2.9			
Total	578	100			

Legend: Very Low: 0-45; Low: 46-90; Average: 91-135; High: 136-180; Very High: 181-226

Generally, the majority of the students feel an optimal level of mental health. The respondents in this study showed a higher mental health index as compared to the respondents of Argao et al. (2021) who had a below-average mental health index, and in contrast to the study of Broglia et al. (2021), where students were reported to have high levels of social anxiety, generalized anxiety, and academic distress.

Mental Health Index Subscales

Table 5. *Mental Health Index Subscales*

<i>Level</i>	<i>Anxiety</i>		<i>Depression</i>		<i>Loss of Behavioral Control</i>		<i>General Positive Affect</i>		<i>Emotional Ties</i>		<i>Life Satisfaction</i>	
	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Low	44	7.6	32	5.5	13	2.2	28	4.8	80	13.8	131	22.7
Average	534	92.4	503	87	564	97.6	550	95.2	498	86.2	435	75.3
High	0	0	43	7.4	1	0.2	0	0	0	0	12	2.1
Total	578	100	578	100	578	100	578	100	578	100	578	100

Legend: Anxiety - Low: 0-18; Average: 19-36; High: 37-54; Depression - Low: 0-7; Average: 8-15; High: 16-23; Loss of Behavioral or Emotional Control - Low: 0-17; Average: 18-34; High: 35-53; General Positive Affect - Low: 0-20; Average: 21-40; High: 41-60; Emotional Ties - Low: 0-4; Average: 5-8; High: 9-12; Life Satisfaction - Low: 0-2; Average: 3-4; High: 5-6

Table 5 shows the level of Mental Health Index per subscale. For the anxiety subscale, 534 or 92.4 percent have an average level of anxiety, while 44 or 7.6 percent have a low level of anxiety. For depression subscale, 503 or 87 percent have an average level of depression, while 43 or 7.4 percent have a high level of depression and 32 or 5.5 percent have a low level of depression. For the loss of behavioral control subscale, 564, or 97.6 percent, of the population scored average while 13 or 2.2 percent scored low and 1 or 0.2 percent scored high. For the general positive affect subscale, 550 or 95.2 percent of the population scored average and 28 or 4.8 percent of the population scored low. For the emotional tie's subscale, 498 or 86.2 percent of the population scored average, while 80 or 13.8 of the population scored low. For the life satisfaction subscale, 435 or 75.3 percent of the population scored average while 131 or 22.7 percent of the population scored low, and 12 or 2.1 percent of the population scored high.

Contrary to the study of Liu et al. (2019) and Atherton and Cornwall (2022) who mention that their respondents scored higher on depression, anxiety, and stress as well as psychological distress and despite the negative impact of COVID-19 on the Filipino college students' mental well-being and life satisfaction as mentioned in the study of Egcas et al. (2021), the respondents of this study show an average level on anxiety, depression, and loss of behavioral affect as subscales in psychological distress and showed an average level on general positive affect, emotional ties, and life satisfaction as subscales in psychological well-being. This shows that respondents have optimal well-being as compared to the respondents mentioned in previous studies.

Attachment Styles

Table 6. *Attachment Styles*

<i>Attachment Style</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percent</i>
Dismissive	57	9.9
Fearful	406	70.2
Secure	115	19.9
Total	578	100

Table 6 reveals the attachment styles of the respondents. 406 or 70.2 percent of the population have a fearful attachment style while 115 or 19.9 percent of the population have a secure attachment style while 57 or 9.9 percent have a dismissive attachment style. Most of the respondents in the study claim that they fear feelings of unwanted, unloved, or rejected by the people surrounding them. They often crave intimacy and connection. When they show feelings for others, they are afraid that the others might not feel the same about them. Moreover, they often wonder whether their romantic partners really care about them. They often worry about getting hurt when they get close to people. With this, the respondents may have difficulty in establishing relationships and may struggle in trusting people around them due to their experience of insensitive and inconsistent caregiving. They may also struggle regulating their emotions and may have developed low self-esteem.

Consistent to the study of Henschel et al. (2020), the majority of the respondents who had fearful attachment styles had higher emotion

regulation difficulties as compared to secured and dismissive individuals. To Park et al. (2018), those with fearful attachments struggle with seeking and avoiding closeness because of conflicting feelings.

In the Young Adult Fertility and Sexuality Study conducted in 2021 by the University of the Philippines Population Institute (UPPI), it was found out that 25% of the suicide ideators mostly sought help from close friends while only 7% sought help from parents/guardians and 5% from other relatives (Pinoy Youth in Worse Mental Shape Today, Nationwide Survey Indicates, 2022). Moreover, consistent to the study of Ayiro et al. (2023), students tend to disclose their problems to their peers. This showed that the majority of the young generation nowadays seek more help from peers than from their parents.

Level of Help-seeking Behaviors

Table 7. *Help-seeking Behavior*

Level	Frequency	Percent	Mean	S.D.	V.I.
Low	20	3.5			
Average	167	28.9			
High	391	67.6	6.16	1.06	High
Total	578	100			

Legend: Low: 0-3; Average: 4-5; High: 6-7

Table 7 presents that 391 or 67.6 percent of the population with a mean of 6.16 and an SD of 1.06 have a high level of help-seeking behavior and 167 or 28.9 percent of the population have an average level of help-seeking behavior while 20 or 3.5 percent of the population have a low level of help-seeking behavior. Majority of the respondents are able to admit or acknowledge that they need help when struggling with mental health distress. They could easily seek treatment or support whether formal or informal. Majority of the students feel that seeking help from a mental health professional would be useful, effective, and important if they had a mental health concern such as issues ranging from personal difficulties to mental illness. They also see that seeking mental health professional help is desirable and empowering. Finally, majority of the respondents feel that seeking help from mental health professionals such as psychologists, psychiatrists, clinical social workers, and counselors is healthy.

Consistent to the findings in the study of Metz (2023) and Saito and Creedy (2021), those students who were exposed to mental health education had higher mental health literacy and had positive attitude towards help-seeking. In contrast to the study conducted by Roberts (2023) and Velasco et al (2019) where students who struggled with mental health problems, found it hard to seek help due to perceived stigma and lack of mental health literacy, the respondents of this study do not show apprehensiveness in seeking help due to high level of mental health literacy.

Mental Health Literacy, Psychological Well Being, and Attachment Styles as predictors of Help-Seeking Behaviors

Understanding and verifying multiple linear regression assumptions is crucial in accurate model interpretation and prediction. Thus, the researcher run several fundamental assumptions to ensure the validity and reliability of the results. The independent variables have significant relationship with the dependent variable with p-value <.001. Additionally, there is no multicollinearity in data as seen in the tolerance value > 0.1. Moreover, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is < 5 which indicates no multicollinearity. There is also little to no auto correlation found in the data because the Durbin-Watson's result was 1.994 < 2.5. The results to test the assumptions were found in Appendix C.

Table 8. *Predictors of Help-Seeking behaviors*

Model		R square	Adjusted R square	B	Beta	Constant	p-value	F-value
1	MHLS	0.179	0.178	0.042	0.424	0.952	.000	125.948
2	MHLS	0.208	0.205	.042	.426	-0.072	.000	75.492
	MHI			.007	.169			
3	MHLS	0.224	0.220	.040	.410	-0.411	.001	55.146
	MHI			.006	.132			
	CLOSE			.236	.132			

a. Dependent Variable: HSB

*MHLS - Mental Health Literacy Scale; MHI - Mental Health Index; CLOSE - Close dimension of attachment styles

Table 8 reveals three models that are statistically significant. Model 3 shows the best fit as indicated by an F-statistic of 55.146 with a p-value of <.05, suggesting that the model explains significant portion of the variance in help-seeking behaviors. The adjusted R square value of .220 further illustrates that the model can account for approximately 22.0% of the help-seeking behavior variability, highlighting the included predictors' substantial impact. The table also reveals which variable shows greater amount of change in the dependent variable. Every 1 unit of change in the close dimension of the attachment style, there is .236 change in the help-seeking behaviors. Moreover, every unit of change in the Mental Health Literacy (MHLS), there is .042 unit of change in the help-seeking behaviors. Additionally, every 1 unit of change in the Mental Health Index (MHI), there is .006 unit of change in the help-seeking behaviors.

This displays that the model predicts the help-seeking behaviors at a certain portion. There are still factors that predict help-seeking

behaviors other than the mentioned predictive variables. This is congruent with the study of Sari and Asiyah (2022) who claimed that mental health literacy does not directly influence intention to seek help. There are still other factors such as personal contact with someone with mental health issues that may play a significant role. Additionally, consistent with the finding of Xien and Zakaria (2022), parenting styles were found to have negligible relationship with help-seeking. Moreover, there are also barriers to accessing mental health services according to Adiviso (2022). Cost of mental health services may inhibit individuals from seeking formal help. Moreover, feelings of anxiety, shame, and mistrust, lack of family support, and inefficient process of accessing mental health care were also found to be barriers to seeking help (Al Omari et al., 2022).

Proposed recalibrated mental health program based on the mental health literacy, psychological well-being, attachment styles, and help-seeking behaviors

KANDILI: ALAGANG ESCOLARIAN

A Proposed Recalibrated School-based Mental Health Program

In response to the growing need for comprehensive mental health support in educational settings, this proposal outlines a recalibrated school-based mental health program structured around a multi-tiered system of support (MTSS). The MTSS framework aims to provide systematic interventions tailored to varying levels of student needs, ensuring that mental health resources are accessible and effective across the board.

Kandili is a tagalog word which means the sense of solicitude or attentive care and protectiveness. It also means “the care you give to your children.” The recalibrated school-based mental health program aims to create a nurturing and supportive school environment where students feel cared for, understood, and equipped to thrive academically and emotionally.

Rationale:

The majority of students exhibit a fearful attachment style, despite having an optimal state of psychological well-being and a high degree of mental health literacy. A recalibrated school-based mental health program is suggested in order to address the students' fearful attachment patterns and preserve their high level of mental health literacy and optimal wellbeing. The proposed program integrates three distinct tiers, each addressing specific levels of mental health needs among students. This tiered approach not only acknowledges the diverse spectrum of mental health challenges, but also ensures that resources are allocated efficiently, targeting interventions where they are most needed.

Objectives:

- To promote mental health literacy and awareness.
- To enhance support systems for early interventions.
- To address the fearful attachment styles of the students.
- To provide targeted interventions to students identified as at risk or in need of additional support.
- To deliver individualized support for students requiring intensive attention
- To foster a supportive school environment that values and prioritizes mental health while promoting a sense of solicitude and protectiveness among students and staff alike.
- To monitor and evaluate program effectiveness.

Proposed Programs per tier

Level 1: Preventive Program

The program will focus on psychoeducation that talks about mental health literacy and attachment styles. The activities will focus on module-based seminar-workshop on mental health literacy and attachment styles, mental health campaigns, and incorporation of mental health literacy in the curricula. Activities also include mental health capacity building and peer support groups were identified as programs to equip teachers and peers in identifying mental health red flags, respond to immediate mental health concerns, and refer to mental health professionals as necessary.

Level 2: Selective Intervention Programs for Individuals at Risk

Attachment-based counseling and psychotherapy for individuals at risk may be conducted along with a socio-emotional learning program that will give emphasis on building self-esteem and interpersonal skills. Additionally, peer support groups that will enhance relationships will also be part of the program.

Level 3: Specific Intervention Programs for Serious Cases

Counseling and psychotherapy services that uses attachment-based approach will be the program to help students who may need specialized support to develop or rebuild trusting, supportive relationships by addressing attachment issues through activities and approaches such as reviewing early childhood memories, communication skills training, role-playing, rewriting narratives, and repairing attachments in therapy sessions. An in-house wellness clinic will also be developed as part of the in-house mental health

referral system which will be manned by psychiatrists, psychologists, guidance counselors, and other mental health professionals in the academic community.

Program Evaluation

To evaluate the proposed program, regular assessments and feedback mechanisms will be established to measure the impact of the program on student mental health outcomes. The program will use the CEU Quality Management System Forms:

AAF 002 – Curriculum Evaluation Form
HRF 060 – Human Resource Development Activity Evaluation
HRF 120 – Human Resource Post-Training Assessment
Routine Interviews for students and employees

Sustainability and Scalability

To ensure sustainability and scalability of the proposed program, training programs for teachers and staff will be developed to sustain mental health initiatives beyond initial implementation. Partnerships with community mental health organization and stakeholders will be established to enhance resources and support for the program's longevity and scalability.

By adopting a multi-tiered system of support, this recalibrated school-based mental health program endeavors to promote a holistic approach to student well-being. Through strategic implementation of psychoeducation, targeted interventions, and intensive support measures, the program aims to cultivate a nurturing school environment where every student can thrive academically, socially, and emotionally. By equipping educators and peers with the necessary tools and knowledge, the program seeks to establish a sustainable framework that prioritizes mental health as an integral component of academic success and personal growth.

Conclusions

In conclusion, the students are able to recognize and identify mental health concerns and possess basic knowledge about mental health, which enables them to seek help when needed. While they generally report no significant problems or unfavorable symptoms regarding their mental health, some may still experience negative feelings such as loneliness, fear, and anxiety, which could potentially lead to depression. Many students also fear being unwanted, unloved, or rejected by those around them, and they may struggle with emotional regulation. Instead of turning to their families, they are more likely to seek help from close friends due to concerns about rejection and abandonment. The students recognize that seeking help from mental health professionals for mental health concerns is desirable, useful, effective, and empowering. While mental health literacy is a predictor of help-seeking behaviors, other factors, such as psychological well-being and attachment styles, also play a role in encouraging students to seek help. To address these issues, a recalibrated school-based mental health program will be implemented, divided into three tiers: one for the general population, one for targeted individuals, and one for those needing specialized support. This program will focus on increasing and maintaining mental health literacy, creating and training a team of mental health responders, and addressing the students' fearful attachment styles through both group and individualized support.

To maintain a high level of mental health literacy, it is crucial to strengthen information dissemination mechanisms through various platforms, such as symposia, infographics on social media and printed materials, and the incorporation of mental health courses into the curricula. Additionally, programs and activities should be conducted to continuously enhance students' psychological well-being and prevent the onset of negative mental health symptoms. To support this, students should be equipped with skills in building self-esteem and fostering healthy relationships among families, teachers, and peers through seminar-workshops or training focused on self-esteem and relationship building. There should also be continuous encouragement for students to seek support from mental health professionals, which can be achieved by increasing the visibility of mental health programs and enhancing information dissemination about available support services. By improving mental health literacy and facilitating activities that enhance psychological well-being, students can experience less frequent negative mental health symptoms, making it easier for them to seek help when necessary. The proposed recalibrated school-based mental health programs should be implemented with appropriate funding for staff support and resource allocation. A key component of this initiative is the development of an accessible in-house school-based psychological wellness clinic, which will cater to mild to severe mental health concerns and collaborate with psychiatrists, psychologists, guidance counselors, and other practicing mental health professionals within the academic institution. Furthermore, capacity building for mental health advocates within the school should be prioritized, training them to identify and refer students with mental health concerns to appropriate professionals. To ensure the success of these initiatives, school administrators must allocate a sufficient budget for mental health program implementation and ensure the full establishment of a medical specialist team, including clinical psychologists, registered guidance counselors, developmental physicians, and psychiatrists.

References

Adiviso, F. (2022). Mental Health Literacy, Psychological Distress and Help-Seeking Behaviors of Nursing Students During the . . . ResearchGate. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/360013520_Mental_Health_Literacy_Psychological_Distress_and_Help-Seeking_Behaviors_of_Nursing_Students_During_the_COVID-19_Pandemic_1

- Al Omari, O., Khalaf, A., Al Sabei, S., Al Hashmi, I., Al Qadire, M., Joseph, M., & Damra, J. (2022). Facilitators and barriers of mental health help-seeking behaviours among adolescents in Oman: a cross-sectional study. *Nordic Journal of Psychiatry*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08039488.2022.2038666>
- Argao, R.C.C., Reyes, M.E.S., & Delariarte, C.F. (2021 September). Mental Health Literacy and Mental Health of Filipino College Students. *North American Journal of Psychology*, 23(3), 437–452. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/353511438_Mental_Health_Literacy_and_Mental_Health_of_Filipino_College_Students
- Atherton, K. & Cornwall, J. (2022, December 13). Psychological distress and help-seeking behaviour: Chinese international students in New Zealand. *Journal of the Australian and New Zealand Student Services Association*, 30 (1), 48–62. <https://doi.org/10.30688/janzssa.2022-1-04>
- Austria-Cruz, M. C. A. (2019). Academic Stress and coping Strategies of Filipino College Students in private and public universities in Central Luzon. *International Journal of Advanced Engineering, Management and Science*, 5(11), 603–607. <https://doi.org/10.22161/ijaems.511.6>
- Ayiro, L., Misigo, B.L., & Dingili, R. (2023, March 16). Stress levels, coping strategies, and mental health literacy among secondary school students in Kenya. *Frontiers in Education*, (8), p. 1099020. <https://doi.org/10.3389/feduc.2023.1099020>
- Bacelonia, W. (2022, August 2). Senator eyes mental health services in basic education. *Philippine News Agency*. <https://www.pna.gov.ph/articles/1180411>
- Cavioni, C., Grazzani, I., & Ornaghi, V. (2020). Mental health promotion in schools : a comprehensive theoretical framework. *International Journal of Emotional Education*, 12(1), 65–82.
- Collins, N. L. (1996). Working models of attachment: Implications for explanation, emotion, and behavior. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 71, 810–832.
- Cordero Jr, D. A. (2022). Down but Never Out! Narratives on Mental Health Challenges of Selected College Students During the COVID-19 Pandemic in the Philippines: God, Self, Anxiety, and Depression. *Journal of Religion and Health*, 61. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10943-021-01476-3>
- Cormier, E., Park, H., & Schluck, G. (2022, December 10). College Students' eMental Health Literacy and Risk of Diagnosis with Mental Health Disorders. *Healthcare*, 10(12), p. 2406. <https://doi.org/10.3390%2Fhealthcare10122406>
- Duong, M. T., Bruns, E. J., Lee, K., Cox, S., Coifman, J., Mayworm, A., & Lyon, A. R. (2020). Rates of Mental Health Service Utilization by Children and Adolescents in Schools and Other Common Service Settings: A Systematic Review and Meta- Analysis. *Administration and Policy in Mental Health and Mental Health Services Research*, 48(3), 420–439. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10488-020-01080-9>
- Egcas, R.A., Oducado, R.M.F., Cleofas, J.V., Rabacal, J.S., & Lausa, S.M. (2021, December 03). After over a year of pandemic: mental well-being and life satisfaction of Filipino college students. *Pertanika Journal of Social Science and Humanities*, 29(4). <https://doi.org/10.47836/pjssh.29.4.17>
- Golberstein E., Wen H., & Miller BF. (2020, April 14). Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) and Mental Health for Children and Adolescents. *JAMA Pediatr*, 174(9), p. 819–820. doi:10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.1456
- Goodfellow, C., Macintyre, A., Knifton, L., & Sosu, E. (2022). Associations between dimensions of mental health literacy and adolescent help-seeking intentions. *Child and Adolescent Mental Health*, 28(3), 385–392. <https://doi.org/10.1111/camh.12608>
- Gorczyński, P., Sims-Schouten, W., & Wilson, C. (2020). Evaluating mental health literacy and help-seeking behaviours in UK university students: a country wide study. *Journal of Public Mental Health*, 19(4), 311–319. <https://doi.org/10.1108/jpmh-10-2019-00863>, p.1-11. <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/conferences/arts-congress-proceedings/2019/MH-02.pdf>
- Hammer, J. H., Parent, M. C., & Spiker, D. A. (2018). Mental Help Seeking Attitudes Scale (MHSAS): Development, reliability, validity, and comparison with the ATSPPH-SF and IASMHS-PO. *Journal of Counseling Psychology*, 65(1), p. 74–85. <https://doi.org/10.1037/cou0000248>
- Henschel, S., Nandrino, J., & Doba, K. (2019, December 18). Emotion regulation and empathic abilities in young adults: The role of Attachment Styles. *Personality and Individual Differences*, 156, p. 109763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paid.2019.109763>
- Ines, J.V. (2019, February). Filipino College Students' Mental Health Literacy. *DLSU Arts Congress*, 3, p. 1-11. <https://www.dlsu.edu.ph/wp-content/uploads/pdf/conferences/arts-congress-proceedings/2019/MH-02.pdf>
- Iswanto, E. D., & Ayubi, D. (2023). The Relationship of Mental Health Literacy to Help-Seeking Behavior: Systematic Review. *Journal of Social Research*, 2(3), 755–764. <https://doi.org/10.55324/josr.v2i3.726>

- Lai, B. S., PhD, Hoskova, B., MA, Ba, A. R., Colgan, C. A., MA, Ba, S. S. A., & Liang, B., PhD. (2022). College students and COVID-19: Mental health and purpose formation. *Journal of Emergency Management*, 20(9), 65–77. <https://doi.org/10.5055/jem.0609>
- Lally, J., Tully, J., & Samaniego, R. (2019). Mental health services in the Philippines. *BJPsych International*, 16(03), 62–64. <https://doi.org/10.1192/bji.2018.34>
- Liu, X., Ping, S., & Gao, W. (2019). Changes in Undergraduate Students' Psychological Well-Being as They Experience University Life. *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 16(16), 2864. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph16162864>
- Lumaksono, N. a. P., Lestari, P., & Karimah, A. (2020). Does mental health literacy influence help-seeking behavior in medical students? *Biomolecular and Health Science Journal*, 3(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.20473/bhsj.v3i1.19093>
- Lumaksono, N. a. P., Lestari, P., & Karimah, A. (2020). Does mental health literacy influence help-seeking behavior in medical students? *Biomolecular and Health Science Journal*, 3(1), 45. <https://doi.org/10.20473/bhsj.v3i1.19093>
- Malls, G. Z., Baron, M. B. C., Apat, F. A. J., Sagsagat, H. A. A., Pasco, P. B. M., Aportadera, E. T. C. L., Tan, R. J. D., Gacutno-Evardone, A. J., & Lucero-Priso III, D. E. (2021, August 18). Mental health and well-being of children in the Philippine setting during the COVID-19 pandemic. Health promotion perspectives. Retrieved May 1, 2023, from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC8501475/#s8title28>, 2023 from <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC9222847/#:~:text=The%20term%20mental%20health%20literacy,or%20prevention%20%5B1%5D>.
- Mendoza, N., Bernardo, A., & Dizon, J. I. W. (2022). Unattended Mental Health Needs: Adult Students in the Philippines during the Early Weeks of the COVID-19 Pandemic. *Transactions of the National Academy of Science and Technology/Transactions of the National Academy of Science and Technology*, 43(2021), 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.57043/transnastphl.2021.1135>
- Metz, H. (2023, May). Mental Health Literacy and Attitudes Toward Mental Health Help-Seeking Among College Students of Non-Mental Health Professions. CSUSB ScholarWorks. Retrieved July 24, 2023 from <https://scholarworks.lib.csusb.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=2724&context=etd>
- O'Connor, M., Casey, L. (2015). The Mental Health Literacy Scale (MHLS): A new scale-based measure of mental health literacy. *Psychiatry Research*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.psychres.2015.05.064>
- Park, Y., Debrot, A., Spielmann, S. S., Joel, S., Impett, E., & MacDonald, G. (2018). Distinguishing dismissing from fearful attachment in the association between closeness and commitment. *Social Psychological & Personality Science*, 10(4), 563–572. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1948550618768823>
- Pinoy youth in worse mental shape today, nationwide survey indicates. (2022, October 10). UP Population Institute. <https://www.uppi.upd.edu.ph/news/2022/pinoy-youth-in-worse-mental-health-shape-today>
- Roberts, K.A. (2023). Mental health help-seeking behaviors of first-year university students. Digital Commons Georgia Southern University. Retrieved on July 12, 2023 from <https://digitalcommons.georgiasouthern.edu/etd/2583/>
- Sari, N. D. R., & Asiyah, N. S. N. (2022). Mental health Literacy and Self-Stigma on intention to seek professional psychological help. *Journal of Health Science and Prevention*, 6(2). <https://doi.org/10.29080/jhsp.v6i2.746>
- Serrano, J. O., & Reyes, M. E. S. (2022). Bending not breaking: coping among Filipino University students experiencing psychological distress during the Global Health Crisis. *Current Psychology*, 42. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12144-022-03823-3>
- Veit, C. T., & Ware, J. E. (1983). The structure of psychological distress and well-being in general populations. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 51(5), 730.
- Velasco, A., Cruz, I., Billings, J., Jimenez, M., & Rowe, S. (2020, June 11). What are the barriers, facilitators and interventions targeting help-seeking behaviours for common mental health problems in adolescents? A systematic review - BMC psychiatry. BioMed Central. Retrieved July 24, 2023 from <https://bmcp psychiatry.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12888-020-02659-0>
- Villa, K. de. (2022, October 26). Just 3 mental health pros per 100,000 Pinoy; DOH training more. INQUIRER.net. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1684893/just-3-mental-health-pros-per-100k-pinoys-doh-training-more>
- Xiong, X., & Yang, Z. (2020). Asian international students' help-seeking and help-receiving intentions in American postsecondary institutions. Semantic Scholar. <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Asian-international-students%E2%80%99-help-seeking-and-in-Xiong-Yang/7d4ddef43200ce2e0a47ede60942b315747fe8cd>
- Xu, T., Tomokawa, S., Jr, E. R. G., Mannava, P., Nagai, M., & Sobel, H. (2020a, March 5). School-based interventions to promote adolescent health: A systematic review in low- and middle-income countries of who Western Pacific region. *PLOS ONE*. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0230046>

Xu, T., Tomokawa, S., Jr, E. R. G., Mannava, P., Nagai, M., & Sobel, H. (2020a, March 5). School-based interventions to promote adolescent health: A systematic review in low- and middle-income countries of who Western Pacific region. PLOS ONE. <https://journals.plos.org/plosone/article?id=10.1371%2Fjournal.pone.0230046>

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Mark Vincent F. Reyes

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines

Sheila Marie G. Hocson

Polytechnic University of the Philippines – Philippines